

The Mass of Young Stars likes to play Hide & Seek

Eleonora Fiorellino

Konkoly Observatory, Research Centre for Astronomy and Earth Sciences, Eötvös Loránd Research Network (ELKH), Konkoly-Thege Miklós út 15-17, 1121 Budapest, Hungary

Star formation is not an efficient process. Typical values of efficiency for low-mass stars ($< 2M_{\odot}$) ranges between 0.20 and 0.40 [1, and references therein]. At the same time, the mass accretion rate (\dot{M}_{acc}) measured for Class II young stars (or Classical T Tauri stars, CTTs) are too small ($10^{-7} - 10^{-12} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$, [2]) to build solar-type stars, when integrated for the observed timescales (0.5 – 2 Myr, [3]). The question which naturally comes up is how stars gain their mass during their formation from the prestellar cores collapse to the main sequence entrance, through the magnetospheric accretion scenario [4]. We believe that the most effective way to answer this question is to investigate the mass accretion rate during the early stages of the star formation (Class 0 and I).

We will focus on Class I young stellar objects (YSOs), the evolutive stage of the star formation process when the forming star is still surrounded by the envelope, as in the previous stage (Class 0). However, even if the spectral energy distribution (SED) of Class I is still dominated by the IR-excess, it is possible to observe the photosphere contribution in the near-IR (NIR). In particular, we will discuss the relation between \dot{M}_{acc} , the disk mass (M_{disk}), and the stellar mass (M_{\star}) for a sample of nearby (< 500 pc) Class I YSOs.

The $\dot{M}_{acc} - M_{\star}$ relation

The most precise method to compute $\dot{M}_{acc} = \frac{5 L_{acc} R_{\star}}{4 G M_{\star}}$ [4] of young stars is by measuring L_{acc} directly from the Balmer-jump in the ultra-violet (UV), and by computing the stellar parameters from the theoretical evolutive models. As a consequence, \dot{M}_{acc} has been well studied in a systematic manner for optically visible Class II sources (e.g. [2]), while characterizing accretion in Class I is challenging due to large extinctions, with only a handful of sources observed (see [5]). The situation changed after empirical relations between the accretion luminosity L_{acc} and NIR accretion tracers fluxes were computed with unprecedented small errors [9]. These empirical relations were used to analyze KMOS observations of Perseus NGC1333 cluster (< 1 Myr), providing the only \dot{M}_{acc} survey in Class I YSOs [6]. This study consists currently in the largest sample of Class I for which the accretion luminosity (L_{acc}), the stellar parameters, and, thus, \dot{M}_{acc} are computed. According to these data, Class I \dot{M}_{acc} in NGC1333 is larger up to 2 orders of magnitude in log-scale than Class II, where the most accreting objects are the most veiled ones. However, to draw robust conclusions on Class I in general, further observations are needed.

We selected a sample of 50 YSOs among the nearby (< 500 pc) Class I [7] for which the veiling, the apparent magnitude, and the $\text{Br}\gamma$ equivalent width (EW) were al-

ready measured. We computed their distances using *Gaia dr2* results on single sources, when available, or on the relative star-forming region, and we used them to calculate the $\text{Br}\gamma$ flux from the EW. We used SED-BYS v.2.0 python-based package [8] to extract photometry and build SEDs from which we computed the bolometric luminosity (L_{bol}) [6]. Assuming the age of the sources between the birthline and 1 Myr, we adopted a self-consistent method which links together L_{bol} , $L_{\text{Br}\gamma}$ and IR colors to analyse Class I protostars. In this way, for each protostar, we derived the spectral type (SpT), the extinction (A_V), the stellar radius (R_{\star}), M_{\star} , and L_{acc} (e.g., [5],[6]). Finally, we estimated \dot{M}_{acc} , finding values between $\sim 10^{-8}$ and $5 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot}/\text{yr}$.

Figure 1: The $\dot{M}_{acc} - M_{\star}$ distribution of Class I (red and blue as described by the legend) compared with the same distribution on Class II (empty circles). Pink and black segments show the low-veiled ($r_K < 3$) and high-veiled ($r_K > 3$) mass accretion rates for Perseus Class I [6]. The grey solid line shows the best fit for the Lupus Class II sample [9]. The grey dashed-dotted line shows the best fit for Perseus Class II sample [6]. The dashed black line represents a linear relation with a unitary slope. Figure taken from Fiorellino et al. 2022, submitted.

Figure 1 shows the distribution $\dot{M}_{acc} - M_{\star}$. The fact that \dot{M}_{acc} is larger in Class I than in Class II is here confirmed and enhanced. In particular, we note that Class I \dot{M}_{acc} is larger than for Class II with similar masses for low-mass sources (up to $2.5 M_{\odot}$), while sources with $M_{\star} > 2.5 M_{\odot}$ show accretion rates compatible with Class II distribution. Considering only low-mass sources, we note

that all the highly veiled Class I in our sample have $\dot{M}_{acc} > 10^7 M_{\odot}/yr$. Because of the uncertainty on the age, we did not fit the Class I distribution (red and pink filled circles). However, we plot a linear relation (dashed black line) with a unitary slope to guide the reader observing that Class I seem to present a flatter distribution with respect the Class II sources (empty circles).

The $\dot{M}_{acc} - M_{disk}$ relation

For 33 out of the 50 Class I we analyzed, we have collected measurements of suitable flux densities at (sub)millimeter wavelengths across the literature and the archival interferometric data. Assuming optically thin regime, we calculated the dust mass with equation: $M_{dust} = \frac{D^2 F_{\nu}}{\kappa_{\nu} B_{\nu}(T_{dust})}$, where D is the distance to the source, B_{ν} is the Planck function for dust temperature T_{dust} , F_{ν} and κ_{ν} are the flux and the dust opacity at the frequency of the observation ν . We note that the optically thin regime can be not satisfied, in this case our estimates provide a lower limit on the dust mass measurement. Dust temperature of 30 K is assumed, dust opacity value is $0.00899 \text{ g cm}^{-2}$, and spectral emissivity slope β is set to 1. With uniform assumptions on dust properties we are not introducing additional discrepancy between the disks measured within different observing projects. The disk mass ($M_{disk} = M_{dust} + M_{gas}$) is obtained by assuming a gas-to-dust ratio of 100.

Figure 2 presents $\dot{M}_{acc} - M_{disk}$ over disk masses. The Class I systems are matching a trend seen for Class II disks in Lupus star-forming region [2]. We also compare our results with three evolutionary tracks provided by magneto-hydrodynamic (MHD) disk winds theoretical models which predict different slopes in the $\dot{M}_{acc} - M_{disk}$ diagram [10]. Figure 2 shows that the slope of the evolutionary track changes when MHD disk wind effect are introduced on the viscous model [11], from shallower slopes for disk wind with magnetic field strength decreasing with time, to become completely flat (constant accretion rate with decreasing mass) for constant magnetic field strength with disk evolution. The viscous model is obtained considering initial disk mass $M_0 = 1M_{\odot}$ and $t_{\nu} = 10^5 \text{ yrs}$ [11]. Hybrid of viscous and MHD disk wind evolution is done following Eqs. 60 and 61 in [10]. Our results suggest that purely MHD disk wind evolution of the accretion disk does not reproduce the evolution from Class I to Class II. However, we stress that we cannot properly test these models with our sample, since both the magnetic effects and the disk viscous timescale depend on the environmental effects, while our sample is composed by sources from many different regions.

Conclusions and future steps

We summarise two important conclusions of this work. First, we highlight that a bias is present in our sample. To analyse Class I YSOs we need an estimate of the veiling, which is possible only for low-veiled sources. Considering only low-veiled young stars, we are studying only the less accreting objects. Therefore, we can interpret these results as lower limits among Class I YSOs. Second, observations of single star-forming clouds and models that include earliest stages of disk formation are necessary to further constrain the disk wind model and properly compare different evolutionary stages of young stars.

Figure 2: Mass accretion rate vs. disk dust mass. Red filled circles are the solution of our sample. Purple filled circles are other Class I, and orange filled circles are Class 0. Empty circles are Class II from Lupus sample. Dashed lines correspond to evolutionary tracks for three cases: pure viscous evolution (pink), hybrid of viscous and wind (light blue) and pure MHD disk wind (brown). Figure taken from Fiorellino et al. 2022, submitted.

References

- [1] Fiorellino, E., et al. 2021, MNRAS, 500, 4257
- [2] Manara, C., et al. 2022, 2022arXiv220309930M
- [3] Enoch, M., et al. 2009, ApJ, 692, 973
- [4] Hartmann, E., et al. 2021, ARA&A, 54, 135
- [5] Antonucci, S., et al. 2011, A&A, 534, 32
- [6] Fiorellino, E., et al. 2021, A&A, 650, 43
- [7] Connelley, M., & Greene, T., 2010, AJ, 140, 1214
- [8] Davies, C. L., 2021, SoftwareX, 14, 100687
- [9] Alcalà, J., et al. 2017, A&A, 600, 20
- [10] Tabone, B., et al. 2021, A&A, 650, 192
- [11] Lodato, G., et al. 2017, MNRAS, 472, 4700

Short CV

- 2014: Bc in Physics & Astrophysics, La Sapienza University, Rome, Italy
- 2017: MSc in Astrophysics & Astronomy, La Sapienza University, Rome, Italy
- 2017–2020: PhD in Astronomy, Astrophysics & Space Science, PhD program: La Sapienza and Tor Vergata Universities, and INAF Institute, Rome, Italy
- 2019–2020: ESO Studentship, Garching, Germany
- 2020–present: ERC Postdoctoral Fellowship, Konkoly Observatory, CSFK, Budapest, Hungary